

An Empirical Review of the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Work Performance

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Abstract

School development is the main cornerstone in Educational institutions. All undertakings in the school are controlled by the head teacher. In any case, the head teacher should know about their jobs in affecting educator's responsibility and positively affect their school climates, which will enhance the work execution. Several studies have been done in the education sector, which affecting performance, such as motivation ,need for achievement and competence. Moreover

Previous studies recommended for more studies in the field of; emotional intelligence. However, emotional intelligence is concerned about managing own feelings and the ability to handle that feeling for positive results effectively; the ability to be motivated to complete work, be creatively expressive to maximum capacity; becoming sensitive enough and managing relationships in a professional and matured manner. Many research studies revealed that emotional intelligence had a significantly positive correlation with work performance and that improves the quality of decision making of the leadership and administrative executives .In addition ,emotional intelligence has a meaningful aspects of work performance, employees whom can assess them self is better in communicating skills comparing to others who don't have emotional intelligence, and they are able to achieve job goals and constantly high level of performance Therefore the main purpose of this paper is to examine the existing literature of the relationship between emotional intelligence and work performance .

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence; Work performance; School Headteacher

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Within the past three decades, emotional intelligence has continued to be studied in the research studies (Goleman,2001;Goleman et al. 2002; Hopper,2005).Despite the fact that a lot has been done in ensuring that people understand the benefits of emotional intelligence to the principals in the public and private sectors. On the other hand, no adequate researches have been channeled towards its impact on the education sector, particularly mandatory school (Jain,2014; Dhani et al.2017) compulsory Education is considering the key source of developing academic competence in the education process and providing to the students. School administrators must provide high quality service to their students and have the ability and responsibility to solve the problems inside the school environment .In addition ,they are competent in the professions they are trained for and play a role in inspiring a comfortable climate in the school (Suryadi,2007).According to (Entisar,2014) revealed that there is a weakness in the school administration and poor management in the primary school dynamism and instability in the same school because of continuous movements for the head teachers from their workplace to another . In addition, effective headteacher school not only created good working climates .Also includes teachers perceptions aspects of climates and clarity of vision and teamwork (Atkinson , 2012)

A study by Todd (2006) revealed that the performance of head teachers was always associated with emotional intelligence along with other factors ,and can significantly increase student emotional intelligence and their needs in the school. Moreover, in the study conducted by Hwang (2007), his results exposed that there is a high level of relationship between the effectiveness of the performance for an administrator and emotional intelligence.

1.2 Emotional Intelligence (EI)

Woolfolk et al. (2008) defined EI as the capability to receive information related to emotions, process that information effectively and make efficient judgment acting on that emotion. However, Emotional intelligence has also often been defined as the ability to recognize our own feelings better than others can ensure efficient motivate and efficiently manage our own emotions and relationships (Goleman, 2005).

According to Salovey and Mayer (2002) who tried to introduce a scientific conceptualization of EI, they defined emotional Intelligence as “the ability of an individual to monitor his personal feelings as well as that of other people and it also encompasses the ability to distinguish between them and then make use of the information in guiding both thought and actions”. Both Akers and Porter (2015) stated that EI is the level of a person's capacity in understanding people in general, as well as identifying the key factors that motivate them in working in tandem with each other.

Emotional intelligence is defined as the ability of human beings to observe and handle their own feelings and emotions as well as that of other people. In addition, It is also the ability to recognize different passions and decide if they are appropriate or not. It encompasses the ability to acquire knowledge to control behaviors, conduct, emotions, and supervise them in order , fulfills one’s goals and purposes (Fiori et al. 2014).

Therefore, emotional intelligence is considered one of the important factors that influence the work performance for workers. Moreover, the performance of an employee in a workplace is usually weighed by the accomplishment and assessment of that employee in the organization in order to improve performance and make the organization more effective and proficient (Mshellia, 2016) .

Chira (2010) took the definition to a slightly deeper level; she defined emotional intelligence as the capacity of an individual in understanding everything about his or her emotions. This understanding ranges from self-awareness, self-expression, self-control as well as the ability to recognize the emotions of other people, objects as well as artworks. This definition is clear and concise, and it enables a reader to gain a clearer understanding of emotional intelligence.

1.3 Work Performance

There are several definitions from various perspectives for work performance. The definition of work performance requires the definition of performance. The definition of performance , according to Harbour (2009) is that it is the instigation and execution of some set of actions. It was further explained that the actions could be in the form of achievements, results or some outcomes. As a result, There have been different definitions given to the concept of work performance, but for the purpose of this research work, the argument of Kirby (2005) would be adopted when he argued that there is a need for a coherent definition of the concept to avoid confusion .

Work performance has become one of the trending subjects of the discourse of the years because of the competition that has graced most sectors of the world. The need to maintain and stay ahead of the competition has made many organizations shift their attention towards ensuring that work performance is used at their advantage and because of this, it is now seen as a vital concept in accomplishing the aims and objectives of any organization (Richard et al., 2009). It has been observed that the demands of different stakeholders in the organization have resulted in the need to commit fully to the construct of work performance.

These demands include the governing bodies’ demand for accountability, media and public demand for transparency and scrutiny, and managers and government agencies’ demand for commitment have been observed to be contributing to the need for organizations to commit to the construct of work performance (Poister, 2003).

1.4 Emotional Intelligence and Work Performance

There is an agreement among authors that Emotional Intelligence is positively related to work performance of the individuals. Moreover, it helps in improving equality and help in the decision making of the leadership and administrative executives. Several studies have investigated the relationship that exists between Emotional Intelligence and work performance (Mshellia, 2016; AlHamddan, 2017; Alam, 2016) and they reported that a positive relationship between measuring emotional intelligence and work performance. Emotional intelligence has a meaningful aspect of work performance, employees whom can assess them self are better in communicating skills comparing to others who don't have emotional intelligence, and they are able to achieve job goals and constantly high level of performance. Moreover, Mohamad & Jais (2016) investigates the role of emotional intelligence in teachers' performance; he reveals that in order to keep high levels of job performance, emotional intelligence should be improved through systematic approaches.

On the other hand, Greenidge et al. (2014) showed the relationship between emotional intelligence and contextual performance with the use of structural equation model techniques for analysis; their findings revealed that job satisfaction partially mediated the association between the ability-based emotional intelligence, regulation of emotion, and contextual performance. Furthermore, Jani and Vyas (2014) examined Emotional Intelligence and its impact on team performance. They revealed that how each of these variables, individual and team leader's emotional intelligence influences the general performance of any organization. They also concluded that there is a relationship between the several factors of emotional intelligence with team performance. Also, Jahuras, (2016) investigates Emotional intelligence and its impact on the performance of an elementary school principal. They revealed that how each of these variables, individual and team leader's emotional intelligence influences the general performance of any organization. On the other hand, Vratskikh (2016) investigated the influence of emotional intelligence on work performance and job satisfaction as well as the mediating role of job satisfaction on work performance among administrative employees. Their findings proved that emotional intelligence is correlated positively with important work manners. In addition, Mshellia et al. (2016) investigated the effect of Emotional Intelligence on the performance of nursing professionals in Nigeria. Results revealed that emotional management, emotional self-awareness and emotional, social-awareness have an insignificant positive effect on performance. It was also reported that emotional empathy, emotional self-management, emotional awareness and emotional, social-skills have a significant positive effect on performance. Furthermore, AlHamddan et al. (2017) examined the impacts of emotional intelligence on performance in six Jordanian hospitals and found that emotional intelligence has significant positive relationships with work performance.

Moreover, Another research study carried out by Yoke and Pantick (2016) about job satisfaction as a mediating factor in the relationship between emotional intelligence and perceived performance. They revealed that job satisfaction has an insignificant mediating impact on the relationship between emotional intelligence and perceived performance.

Additionally, Akram (2017) investigated organizational commitment as a mediating factor on the linkage of emotional intelligence and work performance in the higher education sector of Pakistan. It concluded that there is a significant positive impact of emotional intelligence on organizational commitment and work performance. Moreover, the organizational commitment showed a significant effect on teacher's work performance. The results revealed that organizational commitment is a mediating factor in the relationship between emotional intelligence and work performances.

Aritzeta ,(2016) also found a positive correlation between emotional intelligence, job satisfaction, and performance. It was also found that the emotional intelligence of managers is more positively correlated with job satisfaction for employees that have low emotional intelligence when compared to those that have high emotional intelligence. The significance of these findings is dependent on the control of some personal characteristic factors.

There is better quality in the private education sector in comparison with the public, but there is a lack of commitment on the part of the teachers in the private sector because of lack of job security and because of the fact that autocratic style is mostly used by principals in the private sector. Therefore, recommended that the vision and values of the schools should be shared with teachers so as to create a peaceful environment for both the leaders and the led (Alam ,2017) .

Asrar-ul-Haq et al., (2017), the impact of emotional intelligence can be significantly felt about the job performance of teachers. Such that it is an important instrument employed in the adjustment of their emotions and the societal challenges they are facing. Teachers that are emotionally intelligent have improved performance. However, it was revealed that emotional intelligence has a positive relationship with the outcomes of work mostly when it has to do with the education sector. While Baale (2010) point out that a low correlation between EI and leadership effectiveness among head teachers as well as they do not pay attention to the non cognitive elements in their leadership job .

1.5 Conceptual Framework

1.6 Conclusion

Emotional intelligence influenced the work performed in a positive manner as mentioned in literature, and this is highlighted effect about work performance, such as emotional empathy, emotional self-management, emotional awareness and emotional, social-skills have a significant positive effect on performance. The Findings proved that emotional intelligence is correlated positively with important work manners. However, head teachers that are emotionally intelligent have improved performance. However, it was revealed that emotional intelligence has a positive relationship with the outcomes of work mostly when it has to do with the education sector.

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